

PRIMARY SOURCE FOR SOYBEAN IN THE IRRIGATED CONDITIONS OF UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7157257>

Annotation. In this article, the research results of 236 samples of soybean varieties brought from different soybean-growing countries and international scientific centers on valuable economic characteristics are highlighted. Also, crossbreeding was done between plants selected for favorable traits and characteristics, and the laws of inheritance and variation of characters were studied in F₁-F₄ generations.

Keywords. Soybean, cultivar, selection, initial source, seed, disease, pest, heat, drought, dormancy, yield, grain quality

Introduction. Globally, problems related to global warming are leading to a decrease in the yield of agricultural crops. In particular, the drop in daily average air temperature from +21°C and rise from +32°C in the soybean crop disrupts the pollination process and causes shedding of mother flowers, resulting in a decrease in productivity. Breeding and seed production is focused on research activities in countries with a developed soybean industry, such as Brazil, the USA, Argentina, Canada, China, India and Russia in order to create varieties with high yields, early maturity, resistance to lodging, diseases and pests, and the seeds contain a lot of oil and protein.

One of the topical issues of our time is the creation of new soybean varieties that are productive for sowing in the regions of our republic, have high technological indicators of grain quality, do not spoil, are intended for harvesting using mechanization, and are resistant to diseases and pests, and organize their primary seed production.

Research methods. For phenological observation, field and laboratory analysis, "Method of the All-Russian Research Institute of Plant Science" (1984), and for biometric analysis "Method of conducting agrotechnical field experiments on oil crops" (2010), "Method of the State Commission for Testing Agricultural Crops" (1985, 1989), methods of O.Rebrova and B.Dospekhov for the processing of variational statistical data of the research results, the large-smallness of the dominance level (hp) indicator was implemented based on the formulas given in the work of G.Beil and R.Atkins.

The main tasks of soybean selection are to create varieties with high yield, quick ripening, resistance to dormancy, diseases, and pests, and high oil and protein content in its seeds.

Previous works dedicated to establishing some laws of character variability, heredity, and transmission from generation to generation related to identifying new soybean varieties essential for future production are analyzed in depth.

Primary source. In the research, 236 samples of soybean varieties from the world collection of the Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources and the international scientific centers SIMMYT and ICARDA were studied. Among the studied samples, the most are 78 from North America (USA, Canada), 47 from East Asia (China), 37 from Eastern Europe (Russia, Ukraine). Also, the least of the studied varieties and samples belonged to the Australia.

Geographical origin of the variety and samples studied in the research results

No	Geographical origin	Name of countries	The number of variety and samples
1.	Eastern Europe	Ukraine, Russia	37
2.	Western Europe	France	16
3.	Central Asia	Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan	34
4.	Front Asia	Iran, Turkey (CIMMYT, ICARDA)	17
5.	East Asia	China	47
6.	Australia	Australia	5
7.	North America	Canada, USA	78
	Total		236

Varieties in the catalog of Soybean samples at the Research Institute of Plant Science are divided into nine groups (from 80 days to 170 and more days) depending on the duration of the vegetation period, depending on the main valuable agronomical traits and characteristics; depending on the weight of 1000 seeds - nine groups (from 40 grams to 250 and more grams); divided into nine groups (from 6 to 33 grams and more) according to the yield of one plant.

Among the samples of soybean gene pool belonging to different eco-geographical groups, 147 samples according to the location of lower pods, 81 samples according to the weight of 1000 grains and 87 samples according to the number of pods per plant were selected as the initial source for the selection process.

Plant height. Plant height ranges from 15 cm to 1.7 m and depends on variety and growing conditions. It reaches up to 2.5-3 m in the reclining types. The stem is straight, thick or thin, some are curly.

Depending on the characteristics of the stem, the forms of the soybean are divided into two groups:

- indeterminate form - the bud at their end is vegetative, and under favorable conditions, the growth of the stem and the formation of new generative organs last a long time;
- determinant form - the stem ends with a flower shingle, the growth of the stem ends with the formation of the upper shingle, they grow stronger and produce more than the first ones, and the shade of this shape is considered to be an early ripening.

In the world selection, efforts are being made to transfer the existing soybean varieties to the determinant form.

Plant height is one of the main soybean characteristics that determine the suitability of this variety for fully mechanized cultivation from planting to harvesting. The height of the plant varies depending on soil-climatic conditions, location and agrotechnics of cultivation. According to the morphological indicator, the height of the plant is between 14-150 cm in upright forms, and 250 cm and higher in creeping and ground-growing forms.

Table 2

Inheritance of plant height in F₁-F₄ generations of soybean hybrids.

No	The name of the combinations	♀	♂	M±m	σ	V%	hp
1.	F ₁ K-16 x Nafis	135,0±2,31	140,5±2,43	151,5±3,07	9,5	6,3	5,01

2.	F ₁ K-14 x 8852	115,0±2,42	125,0±2,19	132,0±2,79	8,6	6,5	-2,4
3.	F ₁ 2308 x 9206	120,0±2,23	105,0± 2,32	123,7±2,77	8,6	7,0	-1,5
4.	F ₁ K-11 x 5613	135,0±2,61	110,0±2,45	132,7±3,05	9,4	7,1	- 0,78
5.	F ₁ K-4 x 9177	100,0±2,33	140,0±2,17	132,0±3,26	10,1	7,6	0,6
6.	F ₁ Nafis x Y-300- 3347	140,5±1,99	137,0±2,12	152,6±3,21	9,9	6,5	7,93
7.	F ₁ 7469 x 0-128790	115,0±2,08	130,0±1,87	134,7±3,65	11,3	8,4	- 1,63
8.	F ₁ 464170 x 464132	130,0±2,02	95,0±1,96	123,7±2,80	8,7	7,0	0,64
9.	F ₁ 6806 x K-24	145,0±2,31	144,0±2,16	147,3±4,75	14,7	10,0	5,78
10.	F ₁ K-15 x 6310	152,0±2,21	155,0±2,44	162,7±2,62	8,1	5,0	6,14
11.	F ₂ K-16 x Nafis			148,7±4,24	13,1	8,8	
12.	F ₂ K-14 x 8852			129,6±3,57	11,1	8,5	
13.	F ₂ 2308 x 9206			121,5±3,51	10,9	8,9	
14.	F ₂ K-11 x 5613			132,3±4,14	12,8	9,7	
15.	F ₂ K-4 x 9177			129,6±4,20	13,0	10,1	
16.	F ₂ Nafis x Y-300- 3347			149,8±4,32	13,4	8,9	
17.	F ₂ 7469 x 0-128790			128,6±4,35	13,5	10,5	
18.	F ₂ 464170 x 464132			114,7±4,18	13,0	11,3	
19.	F ₂ 6806 x K-24			156,0±4,53	14,0	9,0	
20.	F ₂ K-15 x 6310			161,1±3,59	11,1	6,9	
21.	F ₃ K-16 x Nafis			146,0±5,35	16,6	11,4	
22.	F ₃ K-14 x 8852			127,2±4,41	13,7	10,8	
23.	F ₃ 2308 x 9206			119,2±4,48	13,9	11,7	
24.	F ₃ K-11 x 5613			129,8±5,11	15,8	12,2	
25.	F ₃ K-4 x 9177			127,2±4,81	14,9	11,7	
26.	F ₃ Nafis x Y-300- 3347			147,0±5,16	16,0	10,9	
27.	F ₃ 7469 x 0-128790			129,8±5,11	15,8	12,2	
28.	F ₃ 464170 x 464132			119,2±5,63	17,5	14,7	
29.	F ₃ 6806 x K-24			145,9±7,67	23,8	16,3	
30.	F ₃ K-15 x 6310			158,1±5,30	16,4	10,4	
	LSD₀₅=			3,7			
31.	F ₄ K-16 x Nafis			143,2±4,13	15,2	12,4	
32.	F ₄ K-14 x 8852			124,8±3,97	14,6	11,3	
33.	F ₄ 2308 x 9206			117,0±4,41	14,7	12,7	
34.	F ₄ K-11 x 5613			127,4±4,67	16,1	13,2	
35.	F ₄ K-4 x 9177			124,8±4,65	15,4	13,6	
36.	F ₄ Nafis x Y-300- 3347			144,3±5,21	15,6	12,2	

37.	F ₄ 7469 x 0-128790			127,4±5,31	16,7	13,7	
38.	F ₄ 464170 x 464132			117,0±6,21	17,1	14,6	
39.	F ₄ 6806 x K-24			145,2±7,14	19,7	15,7	
40.	F ₄ K-15 x 6310			155,0±6,0	17,3	14,5	
	LSD₀₅=			3,6			

According to the researches of T. Wilcox, T. Sedijama, each 10 cm increase in plant height ensures an increase in productivity by 1.12 t/ha. It is noted that the height of the soybean plant is mainly determined by the length of the growing season. In late-ripening samples, the main stem is usually higher, in early-ripening samples, on the contrary, the main stem is lower.¹

In our research, the plant height of F₁ generation hybrid combinations of soybean had an average of 114.7-162.7 cm. The highest indicator was achieved by the combination F₁ K-15 x 6310 (162.7 cm). The coefficient of variation was found to range from 5.0 to 10.0% for F₁ hybrid combinations, 6.9 to 11.3% for F₂ hybrid combinations, 10.4 to 16.3% for F₃ hybrid combinations, and 11.3 to 15.7% for the F₄ generation. Plant height inheritance high dominance in F₁ K-16 x Nafis, F₁ Nafis x U-300-3347, F₁ 6806 x K-24 and F₁ K-15 x 6310 combinations, intermediate dominance in F₁ K-4 x 9177, F₁ 464170 x 464132 combinations and F₁ K-14 x 8852, F₁ 2308 x 9206, F₁ K-11 x 5613, F₁ 7469 x 0-128790 hybrids were observed negative dominance condition. The F₁ hybrid between Nafis and U-300-3347 demonstrated the highest dominance (hp=7.93).

The inheritance of plant height in the studied soybean hybrids is presented in Table 2.

The location of the lower pod. The suitability of the variety for mechanized harvesting is mainly determined by the location height of the lower pod, which depends on the decreasing of the yield. The location of the lower legume is affected by the geographical expanse of the area where the crop is grown, the area of fodder, etc. In addition, only 28% of character variability is determined by genetic factors.

Table 3

Inheritance of lower pod location in F₁-F₄ generations of soybean hybrids.

N ^o	The name of the combinations	♀	♂	M±m	σ	V%	hp
1.	F ₁ K-16 x Nafis	18,0±0,45	16,0±0,53	18,4±0,53	1,6	8,9	1,36
2.	F ₁ K-14 x 8852	12,0±0,41	14,0±0,41	13,5±0,56	1,7	12,8	0,52
3.	F ₁ 2308 x 9206	15,0±0,50	12,0±0,44	13,8±0,54	1,7	12,1	-0,18
4.	F ₁ K-11 x 5613	18,0±0,53	12,0±0,49	15,5±0,79	2,4	15,8	-0,15
5.	F ₁ K-4 x 9177	10,0±0,44	18,0±0,51	14,3±0,57	1,8	12,3	-0,07
6.	F ₁ Nafis x Y-300-3347	16,0±0,51	20,0±0,55	19,8±0,41	1,3	6,5	0,90
7.	F ₁ 7469 x 0-128790	18,0±0,52	20,0±0,52	19,6±0,48	1,5	7,6	0,57
8.	F ₁ 464170 x 464132	15,0±0,51	12,0±0,42	13,8±0,49	1,5	10,9	0,18
9.	F ₁ 6806 x K-24	20,0±0,49	15,0±0,49	17,9±0,51	1,6	8,7	-0,14
10.	F ₁ K-15 x 6310	17,0±0,47	11,0±0,42	15,2±0,54	1,7	11,0	0,40
11.	F ₂ K-16 x Nafis			18,0±0,64	2,0	11,0	
12.	F ₂ K-14 x 8852			13,3±0,67	2,1	15,6	

¹ Wilcox, J.R., Sediyama, T. Interrelationships among height, lodging and yield in determinate and indeterminate soybeans. Euphytica 30, 323-326 (1981).

13.	F ₂ 2308 x 9206			13,7±0,64	2,0	14,5	
14.	F ₂ K-11 x 5613			15,3±0,86	2,7	17,5	
15.	F ₂ K-4 x 9177			14,2±0,67	2,1	14,5	
16.	F ₂ Nafis x Y-300-3347			19,4±0,63	2,0	10,1	
17.	F ₂ 7469 x 0-128790			19,4±0,66	2,0	10,6	
18.	F ₂ 464170 x 464132			14,6±0,61	1,9	12,9	
19.	F ₂ 6806 x K-24			17,8±0,62	1,9	10,7	
20.	F ₂ K-15 x 6310			15,1±0,63	2,0	13,0	
21.	F ₃ K-16 x Nafis			17,7±0,69	2,1	12,0	
22.	F ₃ K-14 x 8852			13,1±0,69	2,3	16,9	
23.	F ₃ 2308 x 9206			13,6±0,74	2,1	14,3	
24.	F ₃ K-11 x 5613			15,2±0,68	2,0	15,2	
25.	F ₃ K-4 x 9177			14,1±0,72	2,0	16,0	
26.	F ₃ Nafis x Y-300-3347			19,1±0,72	2,1	14,9	
27.	F ₃ 7469 x 0-128790			19,2±0,70	2,1	15,8	
28.	F ₃ 464170 x 464132			14,3±0,69	2,1	16,4	
29.	F ₃ 6806 x K-24			17,7±0,73	2,1	16,2	
30.	F ₃ K-15 x 6310			14,8±0,71	2,2	15,1	
	LSD₀₅=			3,6			
31.	F ₄ K-16 x Nafis			17,5±0,72	2,2	13,2	
32.	F ₄ K-14 x 8852			13,0±0,69	2,1	15,7	
33.	F ₄ 2308 x 9206			13,6±0,77	2,4	15,4	
34.	F ₄ K-11 x 5613			15,1±0,81	2,3	16,2	
35.	F ₄ K-4 x 9177			14,1±0,69	2,5	17,1	
36.	F ₄ Nafis x Y-300-3347			18,7±0,71	2,4	16,2	
37.	F ₄ 7469 x 0-128790			19,1±0,72	2,2	15,5	
38.	F ₄ 464170 x 464132			14,0±0,81	2,3	16,7	
39.	F ₄ 6806 x K-24			17,6±0,79	2,1	15,1	
40.	F ₄ K-15 x 6310			14,6±0,69	2,2	13,4	
	LSD₀₅=			3,6			

The analysis of the data on the change in the height of the pod location in different soybean varieties shows that the height of the pod location increases with the duration of the growing season. Thus, the height of the lower pod is different².

Table 4

Inheritance of 1000 grain weight in F₁-F₄ generations of soybean hybrids.

No	The name of the combinations	♀	♂	M±m	σ	V%	hp
1.	F ₁ K-16 x Nafis	150,8±1,26	180,1±1,33	182,0±2,08	6,4	3,5	1,13
2.	F ₁ K-14 x 8852	163,0±1,39	154,8±1,52	166,8±2,95	9,1	5,5	1,94
3.	F ₁ 2308 x 9206	159,0±1,44	144,8±1,44	156,4±3,79	11,7	7,5	- 0,64

² <http://agro-archive.ru/soya/1239>

4.	F ₁ K-11 x 5613	159,2±1,37	163,5±1,58	164,5±2,94	9,1	5,5	1,5
5.	F ₁ K-4 x 9177	163,2±1,42	170,4±1,61	171,8±2,65	8,2	4,8	1,39
6.	F ₁ Nafis x Y-300-3347	180,1±1,39	156,4±1,47	193,4±2,33	7,2	3,7	2,13
7.	F ₁ 7469 x 0-128790	142,0±1,55	153,6±1,51	156,6±2,65	8,2	5,2	1,53
8.	F ₁ 464170 x 464132	133,4±1,60	179,2±1,46	165,6±2,48	7,7	4,6	- 0,41
9.	F ₁ 6806 x K-24	208,0±1,28	167,6±1,45	199,0±1,75	5,4	2,7	- 0,56
10.	F ₁ K-15 x 6310	167,2±1,47	172,2±1,38	174,7±2,53	7,8	4,5	2,04
11.	F ₂ K-16 x Nafis			178,6±2,90	9,0	5,0	
12.	F ₂ K-14 x 8852			163,6±3,23	10,0	6,1	
13.	F ₂ 2308 x 9206			154,9±3,93	12,2	7,9	
14.	F ₂ K-11 x 5613			163,7±3,35	10,4	6,3	
15.	F ₂ K-4 x 9177			170,1±3,29	10,2	6,0	
16.	F ₂ Nafis x Y-300-3347			181,7±4,62	14,3	7,9	
17.	F ₂ 7469 x 0-128790			153,7±3,47	10,8	7,0	
18.	F ₂ 464170 x 464132			162,5±3,04	9,4	5,8	
19.	F ₂ 6806 x K-24			195,3±2,41	7,5	3,8	
20.	F ₂ K-15 x 6310			172,2±3,22	10,0	5,8	
21.	F ₃ K-16 x Nafis			175,3±6,20	12,4	11,1	
22.	F ₃ K-14 x 8852			162,0±5,81	13,6	12,2	
23.	F ₃ 2308 x 9206			154,1±5,63	14,1	17,9	
24.	F ₃ K-11 x 5613			162,9±6,13	15,3	15,4	
25.	F ₃ K-4 x 9177			169,3±5,68	13,6	17,4	
26.	F ₃ Nafis x Y-300-3347			178,3±5,72	15,2	16,5	
27.	F ₃ 7469 x 0-128790			150,7±6,01	12,9	15,4	
28.	F ₃ 464170 x 464132			159,4±5,43	13,7	14,9	
29.	F ₃ 6806 x K-24			191,5±6,38	14,7	16,2	
30.	F ₃ K-15 x 6310			171,4±5,41	18,1	18,1	
	LSD₀₅=			3,7			
31.	F ₄ K-16 x Nafis			172,0±5,69	11,6	13,2	
32.	F ₄ K-14 x 8852			160,4±6,23	14,2	11,9	
33.	F ₄ 2308 x 9206			153,4±6,19	13,6	16,5	
34.	F ₄ K-11 x 5613			162,1±6,42	12,9	16,2	
35.	F ₄ K-4 x 9177			168,4±6,37	13,3	15,8	
36.	F ₄ Nafis x Y-300-3347			174,9±5,92	13,8	15,2	
37.	F ₄ 7469 x 0-128790			149,2±6,19	14,6	14,4	
38.	F ₄ 464170 x 464132			157,8±6,42	14,4	13,9	
39.	F ₄ 6806 x K-24			189,6±6,37	15,8	14,2	

40.	F ₄ K-15 x 6310			170,5±6,35	16,3	13,6	
	LSD₀₅=			3,8			

The F₁ generation hybrid combinations with lower pod location had an average of 13.8-19.8 cm. The combination F₁ Nafis x U-300-3347 (19.8 cm) had the highest rate. The coefficient of variation was found to range from 6.5 to 15.8% for F₁ generation hybrid combinations, from 10.1 to 17.5% for F₂ generation hybrid combinations, to 12.0 to 16.9% for F₃ generation hybrid combinations, and from 13.2 to 17.1% for F₄ generation hybrid combinations.

High dominance was found in the F₁ K-16 x Nafis combination, intermediate dominance was shown in the F₁ K-14 x 8852, F₁ Nafis x U-300-3347, F₁ 7469 x 0-128790, F₁ 464170 x 464132, F₁ K-15 x 6310 combinations, and negative dominance was seen in the F₁ 2308 x 9206, F₁ K-11 x 5613, F₁ K-4. The highest dominance was observed in F₁ K-16 x Nafis hybrid $h_p=1.36$ (Table 3).

1000 grain weight. The weight of 1000 grains in soybean is very big (weight 310-1000 g), big (200-309 g), medium (150-199 g), small (100-149 g), and very small (less than 40-99 g). The influence of the external environment on the variability of the weight of 1000 grains is large, but largely depends on the characteristics of the cultivated variety.

F₁ generation hybrid combinations had an average value of 156.4-199.0 g per 1000 grain weight. In F₁ generation hybrid combinations, the coefficient of variation is 2.7-7.5%, in F₂ generation hybrid combinations 3.8-7.9%, in F₃ generation hybrid combinations 11.1-18.1%, and in F₄ generation hybrid combinations 11.9-16.5%.

Heritability of 1000 grain weight was high dominance in combinations of F₁ K-16 x Nafis, F₁ K-14 x 8852, F₁ K-11 x 5613, F₁ K-4 x 9177, F₁ Nafis x U-300-3347, F₁ 7469 x 0-128790 and F₁ K-15 x 6310, negative dominance condition was observed in F₁ 2308 x 9206, F₁ 464170 x 464132 and 6806 x K-24 combinations. The highest dominance was observed in F₁ Nafis x U-300-3347 hybrid ($h_p=2.13$). Inheritance of 1000 grain weight in studied soybean hybrids are presented in Tables 4.

Grain weight per plant. Seed productivity is determined by the weight of one plant grain, thus this indicator is the most important economical trait. The number of pods per plant is also a relative indicator to describe its productivity, and is used within samples of the same grain size, because the weight of 1000 grains and the number of grains in the pod have variability. Therefore, in all cases, when determining the productivity of a plant, the indicator of grain weight from one plant is used. Grain weight per plant is a complex trait that depends mainly on weather and agro-ecological conditions. The importance of the external factor in the formation of this trait is 71-78% compared to 19-77% of the characteristics of the variety.

In terms of grain weight per plant, hybrid combinations of the F₁ generation had an average of 22.5-31.6 g.

In F₁ generation hybrid combinations, the coefficient of variation was 6.0-10.3%; in F₂ generation hybrid combinations, 6.4-10.2%; in F₃ generation hybrid combinations, 9.4-14.6%; and in F₄ generation hybrid combinations, 10.9-14.1%.

Table 5

Inheritance of grain weight per plant in F₁-F₄ generations of soybean hybrids.

N ^o	The name of the combinations	♀	♂	M±m	σ	V%	h _p
1.	F ₁ K-16 x Nafis	24,2±0,45	29,4±0,55	30,2±0,64	2,0	6,6	1,34
2.	F ₁ K-14 x 8852	24,8±0,37	24,5±0,48	24,9±0,75	2,3	9,3	1,64
3.	F ₁ 2308 x 9206	32,0±0,41	21,8±0,39	29,3±0,79	2,4	8,3	-0,47

4.	F ₁ K-11 x 5613	26,5±0,39	27,6±0,41	27,5±0,92	2,8	10,3	0,98
5.	F ₁ K-4 x 9177	24,3±0,44	16,6±0,42	22,5±0,52	1,6	7,2	-0,53
6.	F ₁ Nafis x Y-300-3347	29,4±0,42	23,9±0,51	31,1±0,66	2,0	6,6	1,65
7.	F ₁ 7469 x 0-128790	33,7±0,51	23,9±0,47	31,6±0,61	1,9	6,0	-0,59
8.	F ₁ 464170 x 464132	24,3±0,38	25,3±0,46	25,3±0,69	2,1	8,5	0,99
9.	F ₁ 6806 x K-24	21,8±0,36	30,4±0,49	28,7±0,75	2,3	8,1	0,61
10.	F ₁ K-15 x 6310	23,0±0,44	24,2±0,47	24,3±0,60	1,9	7,7	1,18
11.	F ₂ K-16 x Nafis			28,9±0,70	2,2	7,6	
12.	F ₂ K-14 x 8852			24,7±0,72	2,2	9,0	
13.	F ₂ 2308 x 9206			28,7±0,75	2,3	8,1	
14.	F ₂ K-11 x 5613			27,4±0,90	2,8	10,1	
15.	F ₂ K-4 x 9177			22,0±0,64	2,0	9,0	
16.	F ₂ Nafis x Y-300-3347			29,8±0,81	2,5	8,5	
17.	F ₂ 7469 x 0-128790			31,1±0,64	2,0	6,4	
18.	F ₂ 464170 x 464132			25,0±0,82	2,6	10,2	
19.	F ₂ 6806 x K-24			28,1±0,79	2,4	8,7	
20.	F ₂ K-15 x 6310			24,0±0,65	2,0	8,4	
21.	F ₃ K-16 x Nafis			28,4±1,14	2,7	9,4	
22.	F ₃ K-14 x 8852			24,7±2,34	2,9	11,1	
23.	F ₃ 2308 x 9206			28,2±1,26	2,8	12,3	
24.	F ₃ K-11 x 5613			27,3±2,28	3,1	12,7	
25.	F ₃ K-4 x 9177			21,6±1,41	2,7	11,8	
26.	F ₃ Nafis x Y-300-3347			29,3±2,51	2,9	12,4	
27.	F ₃ 7469 x 0-128790			30,5±2,29	2,8	10,8	
28.	F ₃ 464170 x 464132			24,9±1,62	3,1	13,4	
29.	F ₃ 6806 x K-24			27,6±1,69	2,9	14,6	
30.	F ₃ K-15 x 6310			23,8±2,23	3,0	13,9	
	LSD₀₅=			3,9			
31.	F ₄ K-16 x Nafis			27,8±3,4	2,6	12,3	
32.	F ₄ K-14 x 8852			24,6±3,12	2,8	10,9	
33.	F ₄ 2308 x 9206			27,4±2,91	2,6	12,2	
34.	F ₄ K-11 x 5613			27,1±2,99	2,7	13,1	
35.	F ₄ K-4 x 9177			21,2±2,79	2,1	12,4	
36.	F ₄ Nafis x Y-300-3347			28,5±3,01	3,1	13,1	
37.	F ₄ 7469 x 0-128790			29,9±3,12	3,0	11,8	
38.	F ₄ 464170 x 464132			24,8±2,91	2,9	14,1	
39.	F ₄ 6806 x K-24			27,1±2,89	2,8	13,6	
40.	F ₄ K-15 x 6310			23,7±3,06	2,8	12,9	
	LSD₀₅=			3,9			

According to the heritability of grain weight per plant high dominance was shown in F₁ K-16 x Nafis, F₁ K-14 x 8852, F₁ Nafis x U-300-3347, F₁ K-15 x 6310, combinations, intermediate dominance was found in combinations F₁ 6806 x K-24, F₁ K-11 x 5613, F₁ 464170 x 464132 and

negative dominance was observed in combinations F_1 2308 x 9206, F_1 K-4 x 9177, F_1 7469 x 0-128790. The highest dominance was observed in F_1 K-14 x 8852 hybrid ($hp=1.64$). The heritability of grain weight per plant in studied soybean hybrids is presented in Table 5.

According to many authors, the productivity of plants depends on the presence of favorable factors during the "seedling - flowering" period, the area of feed, the weight of 1000 grains, the number of seeds in the pod, the height of plants, leaves.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Among the samples of soybean gene pool belonging to different eco-geographical groups, 147 samples according to the location of lower pods, 81 samples according to the weight of 1000 grains and 87 samples according to the number of pods per plant were selected as the initial source for the selection process.
2. In the hybrids created by crossing ecologically and geographically distant samples of soybean within the species, the level of heredity was determined in the generations according to the plant height, the location of the pods, 1000 grains and the weight of grains per plant.
3. In the inheritance of characters, high dominance was observed for plant height in F_1 K-16 x Nafis, F_1 Nafis x U-300-3347, F_1 6806 x K-24 and F_1 K-15 x 6310 hybrids, for location of the lower pod in F_1 K-16 x Nafis hybrid, for weight of 1000 grains in F_1 K-16 x Nafis, F_1 K-14 x 8852, F_1 K-11 x 5613, F_1 K-4 x 9177, F_1 Nafis x U-300-3347, F_1 7469 x 0-128790 and F_1 K-15 x 6310 hybrids, for grain weight per plant in F_1 K-16 x Nafis, F_1 K-14 x 8852, F_1 Nafis x U-300-3347 and F_1 K-15 x 6310 hybrids.
4. Negative dominance in plant height in hybrids F_1 K-14 x 8852, F_1 2308 x 9206, F_1 K-11 x 5613 and F_1 7469 x 0-128790, the location of the lower pod in hybrids F_1 2308 x 9206, F_1 K-11 x 5613, F_1 K-4 x 9177, F_1 6806 x K-24, the weight of 1000 grains in hybrids F_1 2308 x 9206, F_1 464170 x 464132 and F_1 6806 x K-24, the weight of grains per plant in F_1 2308 x 9206, F_1 K-4 hybrids 9177 and F_1 7469 x 0-128790 was determined by.
5. The highest rate of 1000 grain weight was observed in F_3 - F_4 generation hybrids of 6806 x K-24, Nafis x U-300-3347, K-16 x Nafis combinations, it was 191.5 178.3; 175.3; 189.6 174.9; and 172.0 gramms respectively.
6. It was found that the F_3 - F_4 generation hybrids had a high indicator of grain weight per plant in combinations 7469 x 0-128790, Nafis x U-300-3347 and it was 30.5, 29.3; 29.9 and 28.5 grams respectively.
7. The highest level of protein content was found in Madad variety (41.4%), the lowest level was seen in Nafis variety (40.2%), the highest level of oil content was shown in Sevinch variety (25.0%) and the lowest level was observed in Madad variety (22.0%).
8. By cultivating soybean varieties "Nafis", "Sevinch" and "Madad" in irrigated areas, an additional yield of 6.2-6.7 t/ha was created and 29.2-38.2 percent profitability was achieved.
9. The newly created "Nafis", "Sevinch" and "Madad" varieties were superior to the cultivated varieties in terms of their main economic value characteristics.

